

R value has been found to be 1.2 which indicates a d_{e_g} ground state. From the above observations it can be suggested that the overall symmetry of the unit cell is compressed octahedron.

The probable structure of the complexes is represented in Fig. 1.

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Complex Formation of Lanthanons(III) with *o*-(*N*- α Hydroxybenzophenonimino)benzene Sulphonic Acid and *o*-(*N*- α -Hydroxybenzophenonimino)ethane Sulphonic Acid

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THE paper describes the results of potentiometric study of the complex formation of trivalent La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Er with the ligands *o*-(*N*- α -hydroxybenzophenonimino)ben-

zene sulphonic acid (H_2BB) and *o*-(*N*- α -hydroxybenzophenonimino)ethane sulphonic acid (H_2BE) in aqueous media ($\mu=0.01, 0.05$ and $0.1 M NaClO_4$) at 25, 35 and 45°.

Experimental

The ligands H_2BB and H_2BE were synthesised by condensing 30% equimolar ethanolic solutions of *o*-hydroxybenzophenone and orthanilic acid or 2-aminoethane sulphonic acid in presence of a small amount of piperidine as the condensing agent. The resulting yellow crystals of H_2BB and H_2BE were recrystallised from ethanol, m.p.: H_2BB , 192°; H_2BE , 210°.

The potentiometric studies of H_2BB and H_2BE in the presence and absence of lanthanon(III) ions were carried out by Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration¹ technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti² in aqueous media at 25, 35 and 45° maintaining fixed ionic strengths ($\mu=0.01, 0.05$ and $0.1 M NaClO_4$) using an Unitec DPH-77 pH meter equipped with glass-calomel electrode assembly. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - PROTON - LIGAND CONSTANTS (pK_n^H) OF H_2BB AND H_2BE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$

Ligand	pK_n^H	Temp.		
		25°	35°	45°
H_2BB	$\log K_1^H$	4.07	3.83	3.50
	$\log K_2^H$	8.78	8.58	8.24
H_2BE	$\log K_1^H$	4.86	4.45	4.20
	$\log K_2^H$	9.52	9.35	9.08

Results and Discussion

The $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ values (Table 1) indicate the biprotic nature of the ligands. These values decrease with the rise of temperature and increasing of ionic strength in agreement with Hückel's equation³. The values of free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy changes (ΔS°) of the chelates suggest their favourability which are shown in Table 2. A plot of ($pK^H - ct^2$) vs t was found to be linear satisfying the Harned's equation⁴.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES

Lanthanone(II)	Ligand	log β^0			$-\Delta G^{0*}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^{0*}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^{0*} JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		25°	35°	45°			
La	H ₂ BB	8.8	8.9	9.0	50.1	23.6	239.3
	H ₂ BE	8.1	8.3	8.3	46.0	36.3	267.2
Pr	H ₂ BB	9.2	9.4	9.5	52.5	31.7	273.4
	H ₂ BE	8.6	8.6	8.8	48.9	16.3	211.7
Nd	H ₂ BB	9.7	9.8	9.9	55.2	12.7	220.5
	H ₂ BE	8.9	9.0	9.2	50.9	17.3	221.4
Sm	H ₂ BB	10.0	10.2	10.3	57.2	27.2	274.0
	H ₂ BE	9.3	9.4	9.4	53.0	24.5	251.6
Gd	H ₂ BB	10.4	10.5	11.6	59.1	25.4	274.4
	H ₂ BE	9.6	9.7	9.8	54.6	23.6	253.9
Tb	H ₂ BB	10.7	10.9	11.0	65.1	29.0	305.5
	H ₂ BE	10.0	10.1	10.3	57.0	22.7	258.8
Dy	H ₂ BB	11.1	11.2	11.3	63.2	25.4	287.7
	H ₂ BE	10.4	10.6	10.8	59.4	31.8	296.1
Ho	H ₂ BB	11.4	11.5	11.6	64.8	25.4	292.8
	H ₂ BE	10.9	11.0	11.1	62.0	24.5	280.8
Er	H ₂ BB	11.7	11.8	11.9	66.5	27.2	204.2
	H ₂ BE	11.2	11.4	11.5	64.1	27.2	296.4

*At 25°.

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A New Heterogeneous Selective Ion Sensitive Electrode for Lead(II) Ions

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LEAD ion-selective membrane electrode based on electroactive material like precipitated silver sulphide—lead sulphide is known¹. Pungor *et al.*² observed that the electrode surface becomes depleted in lead sulphide, lead sulphate crystals being formed during chemical oxidation and lead oxide crystals during anodic oxidation. The application of various lead electrodes based on lead sulphide have been discussed³. A number of other electroactive materials like lead selenide⁴, lead telluride, lead diisobutyl dithiophosphate⁵, lead(IV) oxide⁶

etc. have been used for the preparation of lead(II) ion selective membrane electrodes. Linder *et al.*⁷ prepared a lead selective neutral carrier based liquid membrane electrode. In this paper we report a new electrode for lead(II) ions in which lead(II) complex of salicylaldoxime has been used as an electroactive material for the ion-selective membrane electrode.

Experimental

Preparation of membrane: Salicylaldoxime (~1 g) was dissolved in 95% ethanol (5 ml). It was then diluted to 100 ml by water and added to ammoniacal solution (pH > 9) of lead acetate to precipitate⁸ the yellow complex PbC₇H₈O₂N which was dried in air.

Lead salicylaldoxime complex (100 mg) was thoroughly mixed with Araldite (Ciba-Geigy) (100 mg) on Whatman's filter paper No. 42. The paste was uniformly spread on the filter paper and then dried in air for 24 h to obtain a membrane of 0.5 mm thickness. The membrane along with the filter paper was immersed in 1.0 M lead nitrate solution and then the adhering filter paper was peeled off.

Preparation of electrode: A piece of membrane was cut out and fixed at one end of a pyrex glass tube (o.d. 0.8 cm, i.d. 0.6 cm) with Araldite. The tube was filled with a solution (0.01 M) of lead nitrate and kept immersed in 0.01 M lead nitrate for 6 days and then for at least 1 h before use. A